

Design, simulation and experimental verification of an active inductance for a low frequency tuned mass damper in an aircraft fuselage active vibration cancellation system

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Abstract-In the context of Clean Sky 2 project TAVAC, technologies for active Vibration and Acoustic Comfort are investigated to be used in business jet aircrafts. More specifically in order to reduce the resulting low frequency vibration on the aircraft tip a Semi-Active Tuned Mass Damper was designed using very large inductances. This paper presents the design, simulation and laboratory prototyping of high value inductances, in the range of 4 Henry.

Keywords-inductance(s), active inductance, aircraft fuselage, active vibration cancellation, piezoelectric tuned mass damper, Hartley Oscillator

I. INTRODUCTION

In aircraft cabin environments, vibrations and noise co-exist, thus affecting the passenger comfort and quality of flight. Vibrations are typically generated by two main sources: (i) the aircraft engines (turbojet or turboprop) rotating at high speeds and transferred via the engine mounts and the fuselage to passenger area; these vibrations typically lay in the range of 100-500Hz. (ii) Additional vibrations are caused by the aerodynamic loads on the fuselage which may affect the global modal response of the aircraft and are finally transferred to the passenger area via the fuselage floor. The latter are significantly lower – up to frequencies of 20 Hz. The wide gap between the two frequency ranges, as well as the different transfer path, requires that each vibration source should be treated and mitigated independently (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. TAVAC vibration and noise cancellation objectives [1]

Amongst the objectives of Clean Sky 2 Project TAVAC [1] is the design of an anti-vibration setup, in order to reduce the resulting fuselage vibration on the aircraft tip, due to the aerodynamic excitation applied on the horizontal tail and to quantify the system performance, with respect to the set targets for vibration attenuation, power consumption, reliability, system weight and so forth.

The anti-vibration setup to be installed in the aircraft cockpit is a Semi-Active Tuned Mass Damper (SATMD). This SATMD configuration is shown in Figure 2, involving the use of an auxiliary mass, linked to a piezoelectric stack actuator.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the semi-active TMD (SATMD) with resistive and inductance components connected parallel to the Piezoelectric stack actuator [1]

The piezoelectric stack is connected to a circuit consisting of two elements; a tunable resistance providing the potential to adapt the level of energy dissipation and a tunable inductance, adding to the system virtual mass and allowing to switch the tune of the TMD.

Seeking the optimal conditions and values in order to operate in the desired frequency range, which is 5 to 15 Hz, we conclude that we need an inductance of the order of several Henry and more specifically close to 4 Henry. The requirement for inductances with extremely high values, when passive inductances are considered, is a barrier not only in terms of manufacturability, but in terms of size and weight too. The need of a different approach is apparent.

II. THE CONCEPT OF ACTIVE INDUCTANCES

The main concept lying behind this different approach, is the use of active (simulated) inductors in the place of equivalent bulky passive components.

The reduction of the size of resistors and capacitors is moderately simple; however, the reduction of inductors is not. Further to the size problem, already mentioned, passive inductors result in undesirable noise and they can produce harmonic distortions, if ferromagnetic materials are being used. For frequencies below 20 Hz in particular, the size and weight of inductors become exceedingly large and Q becomes very low. Hence, inductors are seldom used at such low frequencies

The circuit of Antoniou's simulated inductor [2], which is one of the most commonly used circuits, is given in Figure 3, where two op-amps are being used, together with five passive components.

Fig. 3. Antoniou inductor simulation circuit [2]

Assuming the op-amps perform as ideal, then (i) the non-inverting inputs V_+ and the inverting inputs V_- of the amplifiers will be equal to each other and also (ii) the current in the non-inverting and in the inverting terminals will be zero [3]. The current I , that has been drawn is given by (1), whereas from the second Kirchhoff law in the non-inverting and in the inverting node we extract equation (2) and (3):

$$I = \frac{V - V_1}{Z_1} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{V_1 - V}{Z_2} + \frac{V_2 - V}{Z_3} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{V_2 - V}{Z_4} + \frac{0 - V}{Z_5} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Solving these three equations by eliminating V_1 and V_2 , the ratio V/I is given by equation (4), shown below:

$$Z = \frac{V}{I} = \frac{Z_1 Z_3 Z_5}{Z_2 Z_4} \quad (4)$$

It is obvious that for different types of Z_i the total impedance Z can have various types of behavior and value. One suitable choice of Z_i for the purpose of the pre-mentioned cause is the selection of the impedances as, $Z_1=R_1$, $Z_2=X_{C2}$, $Z_3=R_3$, $Z_4=R_4$, $Z_5=R_5$. Thus, the impedance of the circuit is:

$$Z = \frac{SR_1 R_3 R_5 C_2}{R_4} \quad (5)$$

This is identical as having an inductor with a value given by (6) and it can be simplified more by letting $R_1=R_3=R_4=R_5=R$ and $C_2=C$ resulting to the equation (7).

$$L = \frac{R_1 R_3 R_5 C_2}{R_4} \quad (6)$$

$$L = CR^2 \quad (7)$$

The concept of active inductors enables the following [4, 5,7]:

- The replacement of inductances regardless of their desired value, due to the range of values equation (7) may take.
- When high value inductances are required, as also the TAVAC project demands, then L can take values close to 10 Henry without the use of supercapacitors. For instance, if $R=3.3K\Omega$ and $C=1\mu F$, L is equal to 10.89 Henry.
- The circuit of active inductors, it is easy to design and manufacture, because of its simplicity and it does not require extreme op-amps, contrariwise regular op-amps can be used like the LM-358 series.
- Although, there have been successful attempts to examine and test those inductors, more insight is still needed, on how they perform as a unitary component and their possible use in a variety of present and future applications, where comparable passive inductances were being used.

The next step is to test these active inductors in a simple and frequently used circuit, before trying to fully replace large inductances, in order to record and analyze its operation.

III. HARTLEY OSCILLATORS

A perfect circuit for our purposes is an LC oscillator. Oscillators are basically amplifiers with positive feedback or regenerative feedback (in-phase) and a Basic Oscillator Feedback Circuit is shown in Figure 4 [6].

Fig. 4. Basic Oscillator Feedback Circuit [6]

The feedback network consists of an LC tank and its operation can be described with the help of an inductive coil, L and a capacitor, C . When the switch in Figure 5 is in position A, the capacitor is charged up to the DC supply

voltage V and when the capacitor is full charged, the switch moves to the position B. The capacitor is now connected in parallel with the inductive coil and starts to discharge through the coil, which results in the decrease of the voltage across C and the increase of the current running through the coil.

Fig. 5. Basic LC Oscillator Tank Circuit

This rising current sets up an electromagnetic field around the coil which resists this flow of current. When the capacitor is fully discharged all the electrostatic energy, which was once stored in the capacitor, has now transferred to the inductive coil as electromagnetic energy. The current within the coil will start to fall and a back emf is induced in the coil keeping the current flowing in the original direction and the capacitor once again starts to charge. Finally, the capacitor is fully charged, when the current reduces to zero and the electromagnetic field of the coil has collapsed completely. However the polarity of the voltage changes, as the energy passes back and forth between the capacitor and the inductor, producing an AC sine voltage and current waveform. This oscillation would continue indefinitely if there were no energy losses within the circuit.

An implementation of a Hartley Oscillator is by using an op-amp and one typical design is presented in Figure 6. The gain adjustment is controlled by the feedback resistance and the input resistance. In contrast with the transistorized version, the op-amp version has a gain that is less dependent on the tank circuit elements, resulting in a well-sufficient frequency stability.

Fig. 6. Hartley Oscillator using an operation amplifier.

The sine waveform created by the feedback is coupled with the op-amp, afterwards it is stabilized and inverted by the amplifier, 180° phase shift and this along with the 180° phase shift of the feedback loop, provides the appropriate phase relationship of positive feedback, in order to maintain the oscillations. The frequency of the oscillations is given by equation (8):

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{C(L1+L2)}} \quad (8)$$

This can be simplified even more, by assuming $L_1=L_2=L$ and is shown in equation (9):

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2LC}} \quad (9)$$

IV. HARTLEY OSCILLATOR WITH ACTIVE INDUCTORS

Active inductors and more specifically the Antoniou's inductor will replace the inductances L_1 and L_2 of the Hartley's oscillator and the amended circuit is shown in Figure 7, for operation at $f=12.15\text{Hz}$. The simulated inductors of the Hartley oscillator have been simulated, using the OrCAD Pspice software, in order to evaluate their performance according to the operation frequency of the oscillations and the positive feedback.

Fig. 7. Hartley oscillator with simulated inductors operating at $f=12.15\text{Hz}$.

At this point it is important to mention that the scope of this analysis is only the proper and smooth operation of the Hartley oscillator using these simulated inductors, whereas the possible attenuated oscillations that might be present are

not so important, because they will provide us some true evidence of the pre-mentioned goal. That was the reason why the op-amp version was selected; the enhanced frequency stability that it provides.

The design of the circuit was carried out with respect to the TAVAC project specifications, i.e. the desired frequency range is 5-15Hz. Firstly, assuming that $R1=R3=R5=1K\Omega$, $R4=70K\Omega$ and $C2=50\mu F$, we obtain simulated inductances $L=L1=L2=0.714$ Henry and setting the capacitance $C=120\mu f$, the operating frequency is $f_{theor}=12.15$ Hz.

After the design of the above circuit in OrCAD Pspice and setting the simulation to run for 10 seconds, the expected sine waveform has a frequency close to the theoretical $f_{theor}=12.15$ Hz. In Figure 8 the output waveforms of the nodes V_+ and V_- are shown in a randomly chosen time frame. These are the two nodes of the capacitance C , depicted in order to check the 180° phase shift between them.

Fig. 8. Simulation Results, for $L=0.714$ Henry and $C=120\mu F$.

The simulation results are highlighted below:

- An approximate measurement of the simulation frequency is $f_{sim}=12.04$ Hz, which is very close to the theoretical.
- Also the positive feedback works very well and it is obvious that V_+ and V_- have 180° phase shift.
- The amplitude of the voltage waveforms is satisfactory and varies around 100 mVolts
- The oscillations, although not our primary concern, show a slight attenuation over time.

The simulation gave some very promising results for the use of simulated inductors, however there is still the need of a laboratory verification, thus the next step is to assembly the required experimental set-up.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The construction of the circuit in a breadboard has been carried out without changing anything from the initial design shown in Figure 7. The test results (voltage waveform V_+) are presented in Figure 9 in a common diagram with the simulation signal, for reasons of comparison:

Fig. 9. Simulation and test results, for $L=0.714$ Henry and $C=120\mu F$.

Those very interesting results, show how close to each other are the theoretical, simulation and test results. Starting with a theoretical frequency of $f_{theor}=12.15$ Hz, the simulation revealed a little lower frequency $f_{sim}=12.04$, while the test results presented a slightly higher frequency $f_{test}=12.5$ Hz. These results are very close to the theoretical frequency and it is obvious that the results are very promising. Any deviations between them, could be caused due to equipment-device error or due to non-ideal components.

VI. OBTAINING HIGHER INDUCTANCE VALUES

In this section our attempt to obtain a higher inductance value using the simulated inductors is described, while the specifications of operation in the same range of frequency remain the same. The analysis presented here provides some very important data on the use of simulation inductors, regarding their behavior when reaching high inductance values and the overall circuitry response and corresponding dependencies.

As mentioned the theoretical, or operation frequency, remains the same $f_{theor}=12.15$ Hz when setting $L=4$ Henry, which is almost 5.6 times the value discussed in the previous sections. The value of the capacitance according to equation (9) is calculated $C=21.45\mu F$ and in order to get $L=4$ Henry we simply set $R1=5.6k\Omega$, leaving everything else unchanged.

The same procedure is followed, in order to get the simulation and test results, i.e. the voltage waveform of node V_+ , illustrated in Figure 10.

The results are chosen in a random time frame, the simulation frequency is $f_{sim}=11.91$ Hz and the test frequency is $f_{test}=12.35$ Hz. These promising results are very close to the theoretical frequency, and more specifically they are ranging almost 0.2 Hz around the theoretical frequency. It has to be mentioned that although attenuated oscillations were observed, the attenuation level in the range of 1-4 Henry was at an acceptable level (< -3 dB), which can be easily compensated at the final SATMD development phase.

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Fig. 10. Simulation and test results, for $L=4$ Henry and $C=21.45\mu\text{F}$.

VII. CONCLUSION

TAVAC project, through its anti-vibration system specifications, raised the issue of using high valued inductances, which had to operate in a low frequency range of 5-15Hz. This requirement seemed to be a perfect fit for the investigation of simulated inductors. From a list of different topologies, Antoniou's inductors were chosen to carry out a series of simulations and tests. In order to evaluate their performance in a simple and frequently used circuit, the Hartley Oscillator was chosen. This led in turn to the choice of the op-amped version of the Hartley Oscillator, because of its frequency stability.

The simulations were made with the use of OrCAD Pspice software and the test circuits were measured in a breadboard in lab environment. Starting with a relative high value $L=0.714$ Henry of simulated inductors the results were very close to the theoretical frequency and the positive feedback was satisfactory.

These promising results allowed us to proceed in testing simulated inductors with higher values, i.e. $L=4$ Henry and above, while the desired frequency remained the same. The final results were beyond expectations; the performance was smooth, although there was significant attenuation at inductance values $L=25$ Henry. The simulation and test frequency remained again very close to the theoretical.

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